

Internet “Lingo” Amongst The Youth: Teachers Perspective On Students Language Performance

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Abstract. This study unearthed teachers’ perspective on the influence of internet slang on the writing and speaking skills of the students. This study employed a phenomenological research design which aims to determine the experiences and perceptions of the seven (7) participants. The emerging themes on the perspectives of teachers on the students’ use of internet “lingo” in English Class under the benefits of internet language were evokes emotions and improves students’ creativity while the themes that emerged on the challenges of internet language were multiple and conflicting meanings, and excessive use of internet language. Meanwhile, the emerging themes on the teachers dealing with the challenges of internet “lingo” in the students learning of English language were engaging students to both digital social communications and formal academic discourse, widening vocabulary and sentence mastery, and giving feedback. Lastly, the emerging themes on the educational management insights drawn from the experience of the teachers were internet language improves student motivation, internet language assists language development, and Teacher to Improve professional competence. The results concocted that principals should encourage teachers to integrate internet language awareness to students as part of communication subjects for students to know how to effectively utilize it. Moreover, the results generated provided comprehensive data in conducting future research with similar scope.

KEY WORDS

1. Internet ‘lingo’
2. Formal language
3. Informal
4. Language Curriculum
5. Davao City

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1. Introduction

The rise of the internet and social media use among youth has introduced new forms of communication, often characterized by slang, abbreviations, and emojis collectively known as internet “lingo.” While this language fosters quick interactions, educators’ express concerns about its impact on students’ language skills, especially in formal settings. This study explores teachers’ perspectives on how internet slang influences students’ language performance and the potential implications for education in the digital age. The use of internet “lingo” or slang among students can have both positive and negative impacts on their language performance, particularly in academic settings. While it can enhance communication in informal contexts and potentially boost confidence, it may also hinder the development of formal writing skills and lead to misunderstandings in formal communication. The world has been dramatically

changed as a consequence of enchanting technological advances in this sphere. The ways of living and approaches to communicating with one another have been entirely altered through the adoption of high-tech contraptions. Technology impelled the evolution of mass media in the early 20th century, and mass media revolutionized human communication as a result. The power of mass media has been acknowledged globally as it has immensely influenced and galvanized communication on the planet (Coyle Vaughn, cited in Saeed, 2021). Derakhshan Hasanabbasi (cited in Saeed, 2021) mention that social networking services (SNS), as a result of digital media, have grown popular with the use of modern tools around the world that have been equipped to interact with a greater number of people on a global scale. In a fast-paced society, social networks facilitate convenient and rapid interactions (Saeed, 2021). Al Kadi and Ahmed (2018) mention that English spelling, pronunciation, vocabulary, and grammar have changed since the internet became publicly available, resulting in conflicting views and debate among language researchers and pundits. People's communicative behavior, style, and psychology have all been affected by the subtle influence of internet slang. Corporations have also started employing internet slang in public communications. The more we communicate online, the more users influence the languages of other countries, and the more these changes affect us, because direct communication has a significant impact on language development. Amidst the continuous changes happening to the English language, slang is becoming more and more an essential part of our shifting linguistic terrain. Most new words come from slang. English has become the language of the computer and the internet, and students need to be familiar with contemporary English, and slang will be a significant part of this. The spreading of Internet communication has reached every level of society,

every profession, age, and gender. Nowadays, a significant number of philological works are dedicated to understanding and analyzing correspondence and more to live communication through the internet, which is easily accessible due to various modern principles that clearly illustrate the high degree of technological advancement. Researchers are beginning to define the effects of the use of Internet Slang via text messaging on secondary education, and some researchers are finding negative results between the use of Internet Slang in text messages and test results on academic assignments. The rapid evolution of communication technologies has changed language pedagogy and language use, enabling new forms of discourse, new types of authorship, and new ways to create and participate in communities. Nowadays, internet communication is an essential and valuable part of life, whether the user is nineteen or ninety, a teacher or an engineer, the internet is all over society. It has dramatically changed how people communicate and use English in both writing and speech. As a result, the environment has become increasingly interconnected through synchronous and asynchronous messaging scripts such as text messages, online chat, messengers, emails, etc. Applications like Facebook, Instagram, Twitter, and WhatsApp may also reveal changes that have recently occurred in English. The internet has given rise to what is essentially a new English variety, which is distinct from traditional types. In Indonesia, Many academic societies use Facebook as a medium to exchange opinions, discuss, and share information. They also use Facebook as a medium to improve their ability in foreign languages, such as English. These activities are also conducted by the academic societies of IAIN Bengkulu, particularly the English department students. The students of the English department at IAIN Bengkulu often use Facebook as a medium for exchanging information, discussing a topic, giving comments or complaints, and so on. However, the

way language is used online generally differs from both the way it is used in more formal writing and the way it is used in speech. Many vocabulary words are found in shortened form or abbreviation. The use of those forms is meant to enhance communication. Despite being practical and communicative, the use of abbreviations often leads to miscommunication and misinterpretation. Another problem is that many Facebook users use non-standard abbreviations. It is inappropriate with the standard vocabulary, morphology, and syntax (Riski, 2018). In the Philippines, a study aimed to find the emerging lexical patterns of Netspeak as used by Filipinos, the extent of use of Netspeak in three most popular social media platforms (Facebook, Instagram and Twitter) as well as various domains of pop culture (entertainment, politics, fashion and sports) and its implications to the language studies in the Philippines. The findings showed that the emerging lexical patterns of Netspeak were abbreviations and homophones and that social media platforms and pop culture domains affect the use of Netspeak features. The platform and domain that got the greatest extent of usage of Netspeak lexical features were Twitter and Politics, respectively (Monderin, 2021). The rise of social media has revolutionized communication, particularly among young learners, leading to the widespread use of TXT slang—informal words, phrases, abbreviations, and emojis (Bernabe Cayetano, 2024; Matias, 2023; Paino et al., 2022). Platforms such as Facebook, Instagram, X (formerly Twitter), and TikTok have encouraged linguistic shortcuts like "OTW" (On the Way) and "LOL" (Laugh Out Loud) to adapt to character limits and fast-paced interactions (Muñoz, 2025). While this digital trend has facilitated quicker exchanges and fostered creativity, it has also introduced simplified grammar structures and vocabulary into daily communication (Meleen, 2022). In the context of this research, junior high school adolescents were constantly exposed to TXT slang through abbreviations, informal spellings, and internet short forms. The informal forms, if employed regularly in online communication, can unknowingly migrate into formal writing, resulting in grammatical and vocabulary errors (Matias, 2023). Internet slang users who use these linguistic shortcuts in formal writing exercises undermine their commitment to formal English conventions. Increasing exposure to TXT slang raises concerns about its potential influence on students' formal writing skills, a critical macro skill in English language learning that demands cognitive effort and linguistic precision (Zagada, 2023; Mohamed, 2022). Reliance on informal digital language has been associated with difficulties in maintaining grammatical accuracy and vocabulary richness in academic contexts (Arnab, 2023). Local studies echo these trends: Jeresano and Carretero (2022) observed that while slang strengthened cultural identity among Grade 10 students in Sorsogon City, it disrupted formal writing practices; similarly, Panggaga (2024) reported that SMS shorthand usage among Grade 8 students undermined adherence to Standard English conventions. They use internet slang to express their feelings, thoughts, and ideas. Internet slang is a new term used by members of a group in a specific community. Not all people can understand the meaning of internet slang itself. However, readers, especially English learners, often read without understanding the details of internet slang used by composers. Internet slang has impacted secondary education, with teachers and scholars concerned with the writing and speaking skills of today's youth. Several research studies have been conducted on the impact of text messaging on students' writing. However, there is a lack of research on the influence of internet slang on the academic achievement of secondary school students in the English language. This paper reports on an exploratory study that aims to investigate teachers' perspectives on the influence of internet slang

on the writing and speaking skills of students. The similarities in the participants' perceptions and experiences, as well as their approaches to coping with challenges, will provide valuable insights for developing effective teaching and learning strategies.

1.1. Purpose of the Study—The goal of the study was to investigate teachers' perspectives on the influence of internet slang on the writing and speaking skills of the students. This study

1.2. Research Questions—The primary research questions of this study are the following:

- (1) What are the perspectives of teachers on the students' use of internet "lingo" in English class?
- (2) How do teachers deal with the challenges of internet "lingo" in the students' learning of the English language?
- (3) What learning insights are gained from these experiences?

Since Internet Slang is the language of the current generation of students, language educators, especially in the Philippines, should be familiar with and updated on its features, which they could utilize in their teaching to make the classroom experience for their students more interesting and relevant. The results of this research are expected to provide positive input to English teachers in their teaching of language. In addition, it can help teachers focus on the problem and discuss it specifically to find an improvement solution. Furthermore, this research may enhance students' English language fluency in the teaching and learning process at the Department of English Language Education. It can help students understand the factors that affect their language fluency, enabling them to prepare and develop a good ability in the language. It can present new knowledge regarding the factors that affect students' language ability. With this new knowledge, students can raise awareness of factors affecting their ability to improve and increase their competency. The study's findings may serve as a reference for linguistic studies in the Philippines. Ultimately, the study would contribute to the existing body

of internet slang is important to make people understand the new vocabulary or language expressions developed in societies and how they influence the students' education. In practice, it can provide teachers with ideas on how to maximize the potential use of these words and minimize their negative impact on students. Furthermore, the results generated provided comprehensive data for conducting future research with a similar or relevant scope.

of knowledge in this field and provide a basis for further research. The following were the terms used in this study: Internet Lingo is a non-standard or unofficial form of language used by people on the Internet to communicate with one another. Teachers' Perspective- The beliefs, actions, motivations, and intentions about how one conceives the context of learning. Teaching perspectives give shape and meaning to educational practices, including supervisory practices. Students' Language Performance- is the ability to produce and comprehend sentences in a language. It is the actual use of language in concrete situations.

1.3. Review of Significant Literature—This section presents literature related to the use of internet "lingo" or digital language in academic settings, particularly English language classrooms. It discusses the evolving nature of language in the digital age, the impact of social media on student communication, the emergence of internet slang, and its pedagogical implications.

1.3.1. The Nature and Spread of Social Media and Internet Language—Social media, defined by Kaplan and Haenlein, refers to inter-

active platforms that enable users to co-create, modify, and share content (Kaplan Haenlein, 2010). As social media has grown, so has its impact on language, transforming communication through web-based technologies. With platforms like Facebook, Twitter, and Instagram boasting billions of users, social media has become a major driver of linguistic change.

According to Piskorski (2010), social media platforms meet social needs that are often unmet offline. They have created a new digital culture where expression, interaction, and creativity thrive. Crystal (2011) refers to this as Internet-based language or Computer-Mediated Communication (CMC), which includes emoticons, logograms, and abbreviations. These features are now widely used in both informal and, increasingly, formal settings.

1.3.2. Language Phenomena and Vocabulary Innovation—Language is dynamic and evolves with its users. The influence of technology and youth culture has introduced new vocabulary and linguistic forms into English usage. Tana and Xiaob (2023) and Cong Qian (2021) argue that language must adapt to new contexts, especially online. Arslan (2024) stresses that effective vocabulary learning must now incorporate contextualized, technology-based, and personalized methods to remain relevant. Digital tools such as vocabulary apps and gamified instruction enhance retention and engagement.

1.3.3. The Emergence and Characteristics of Internet Slang—Internet slang, or online lingo, refers to informal, non-standard language used in digital platforms. It includes abbreviations (e.g., IDK, BTW), acronyms (e.g., LOL, OMG), logograms (e.g., 2day for "today"), and emoticons. These linguistic forms are often novel, humorous, and attention-grabbing (Izazi et al., 2020; Rezeki Sagala, 2019). Researchers observe that slang creates a shared identity among digital users and reflects group solidarity, particularly among youth.

However, its widespread use can blur the

line between formal and informal communication. Students often incorporate slang unconsciously into academic work, which raises concerns about its impact on grammar, spelling, and clarity (Wood, 2017; Sakowicz, 2020).

1.3.4. Educational Impacts of Digital Language Use—While some view internet slang as linguistic innovation, others see it as a threat to language standards. Lassiter (2021) cautions that overuse of digital lingo may weaken academic writing and cultural depth. Studies show that heavy reliance on social media can lead to spelling difficulties, poor sentence structure, and a decline in formal writing skills (Arran, 2017; Gilmore, 2021). Students often struggle with research, spelling, and attention to detail due to the brevity and immediacy promoted by digital communication.

On the other hand, Walton (2019) and Bereczki Kárpáti (2021) suggest that internet slang can improve creativity, emotional expression, and language adaptability if integrated into instruction responsibly.

1.3.5. Teaching Strategies and Classroom Implications—Teachers play a vital role in helping English Language Learners (ELLs) navigate the balance between formal English and digital language varieties. Researchers propose classroom strategies such as using games, movies, slang journals, story adaptations, and feedback techniques to teach the context-appropriate use of slang (Elsherif Nsir, 2020; Meyerhoff, 2006).

Marqués-Sánchez et al. (2023) and Silva et al. (2022) argue that digital technologies have redefined socialization and communication, requiring teachers to engage students in both academic and digital discourse. Feedback, especially Written Corrective Feedback (WCF), remains essential to language development (Lee, 2019; Yunus, 2020). Classroom activities that integrate slang within controlled, context-based tasks can help learners understand its function while reinforcing formal language norms.

The literature affirms that the rise of internet language has significantly impacted students' language use, particularly in English classes. While internet lingo introduces creativity and social identity, it also challenges traditional literacy and communication standards. Teachers must develop adaptive strategies to manage this evolving linguistic landscape—balancing innovation with instruction and integrating emerging digital dialects without compromising academic rigor.

1.4. Synthesis—Internet lingo can improve communication and bolster confidence among students, especially within online communities and social media platforms. It can expand vocabulary and expedite communication through abbreviations and truncated forms. Nonetheless, it may adversely affect pupils' academic writing, resulting in problems in language, spelling, and punctuation. Students may find it challenging to distinguish between official and informal language, potentially incorporating slang into academic articles or presentations. Internet slang may result in misinterpretation in formal settings due to its ambiguity and lack of universal comprehension. The prevalent utilization of internet slang may lead to a deterioration in the general quality of English language usage, especially in formal writing. To resolve this issue, it is essential for students to recognize the many settings in which internet slang is suitable and those in which it is not. Educators should underscore the significance of formal writing abilities and offer students opportunity to practice and enhance their academic writing. Fostering linguistic awareness and advocating for a balanced approach to language utilization can assist pupils in maneuvering through the intricacies of language in the digital era. Furthermore, educators encounter a distinct issue due to the emergence of internet "lingo" affecting pupils' acquisition of the English language. The use of casual, shortened language online can impede the acquisition of good grammar,

vocabulary, and pronunciation. Educators must identify methods to integrate technology into language instruction while mitigating the adverse effects of informal online language. Digital communication may present hurdles, including the degradation of formal language, pronunciation difficulties, diminished vocabulary, obstacles in formal writing, and effects on overall communication. Educators can emphasize formal language by juxtaposing it with informal English, adeptly utilizing technology, fostering critical thinking, concentrating on pronunciation, advocating for extensive reading, integrating authentic materials, generating practice opportunities, and offering constructive feedback. Digital communication frequently emphasizes conciseness and informality, resulting in disregard for correct grammar, spelling, and punctuation. Students may encounter difficulties with precise pronunciation, limited vocabulary, and the transition from informal internet writing to serious academic or professional writing. The dependence on internet lingo may diminish clarity and comprehension in formal communication. To tackle these issues, educators should emphasize formal language, properly integrate technology, foster critical thinking, concentrate on pronunciation, promote extensive reading, utilize real resources, establish practice opportunities, and offer constructive feedback. By comprehending these problems and executing successful solutions, educators may assist kids in navigating the intricacies of internet language and cultivating robust English language abilities

1.5. Theoretical Lens—With the interaction opportunities social media offers its users, it is the embodiment of the Social-Interactionist Approach to language acquisition advocated by Lantolf (2000), in keeping with Vygotsky (1978). Social media can provide language learners with new prospects of real-time cultural and linguistic interchange. Besides, from an ecological perspective, which views context as fundamental to language learning, thanks to

the contextual clues it provides and the conversational features it provides, social media can represent ideal sites of language learning. The social-interactionist approach, rooted in the sociocultural theories of Lev Vygotsky, emphasizes the crucial role of social interaction in language development. It posits that language acquisition is driven by a child's innate desire to communicate and actively participate in social activities, with language emerging from and being dependent on these social exchanges. The social-interactionist approach to language acquisition, as advocated by James P. Lantolf and rooted in Lev Vygotsky's sociocultural theory, posits that language develops primarily through social interaction and is heavily influenced by the social and cultural environment. This perspective emphasizes that language learning is not an isolated cognitive process but rather a social phenomenon that emerges from communication and collaboration with others within a given context. Social Agency Theory suggests that incorporating social cues, like internet slang, into instructional materials can make learning more engaging by framing it as a social interaction. Social agency theory is the theory that explains how individuals in society can choose their behaviors. This contrasts with social structure theory (or structuralism), which argues that social structures constrain individuals' actions. A sample introduction for a research paper or presentation on the topic "Internet Lingo" amongst the youth: teachers' perspective on students' language performance" could explore the growing influence of internet slang on students' language skills and how teachers perceive this impact. The introduction would likely highlight the digital culture's impact on language evo-

lution, particularly among young people, and acknowledge the potential benefits and drawbacks of this phenomenon within the context of education. Linguistic Relativity theory suggests that language influences thought. Therefore, the use of internet slang could impact how students perceive and understand language and communication. The internet "lingo" or "textese" used by young people can be seen as an example of linguistic relativity, though not a direct or deterministic one. Linguistic relativity, often associated with the Sapir-Whorf hypothesis, suggests that language influences thought and perception. While the strong version of this theory (linguistic determinism) is largely discredited, the idea that language can shape thought to some extent is still relevant. Another language element becomes marked because of its contrast with the listener's expectation. Further, a marked element is recognized by the parties involved in the exchange as communicating a specific intended meaning. Scholars have argued that in a code-switching situation, the language schema of the words embedded in a message is activated because such words are more salient or marked compared with the matrix language. Below is the framework of this research, outlining the study's objective and the theories presented above. The conceptual framework of the study is presented in Figure 1. Based on the figure, there are two interconnected variables. These variables are the (1) perspectives of teachers on the students' use of internet "lingo" in English class; (2) teachers dealing with the challenges of internet "lingo" in the students' learning of the English language, and (3) learning insights are gained from the experiences.

2. Methodology

This part describes the methodology used in the research, including the overall design, criteria for selecting participants, techniques for collecting data, and the researcher's involvement to ensure accuracy and transparency. It also explains how the data was analyzed and the steps taken to

Fig. 1. Conceptual Framework of the Study

guarantee the study’s reliability and validity. Additionally, ethical considerations are addressed to show compliance with standards that safeguard participants and uphold ethical principles. In summary, this section emphasizes the significance of a thorough and carefully planned approach to investigating the topic and producing trustworthy results effectively.

2.1. Philosophical Assumptions of the Study—The philosophical assumption served as a framework for collecting, analyzing, and interpreting data in a specific field of study. It established the background for the following conclusions and decisions. Typical philosophical assumptions of different types are elaborated below. **Ontology.** This part of the research pertains to how the issue relates to the nature of reality. According to Creswell (2019), reality is subjective and multiple as seen by participants in the study. The ontological issue addresses the nature of reality for the qualitative researcher. The reality was constructed by individuals involved in the research situation. Thus, multiple realities exist, such as the realities of the researcher, those of individuals being investigated, and those of the reader or audiences interpreting

the study. In this study, the realities of teachers on the influence of internet slang on the writing and speaking skills of the students were investigated. In this study, the researcher relied on the voices and interpretations of the participants through extensive quotes, themes that reflected their words, and provided evidence of different perspectives. The answers of the participants to the study were coded and analyzed to build and construct the commonality and discreteness of responses. It is ensured that the responses of the participants were carefully coded to ensure the reliability of the result. The researcher upheld the authenticity of the responses and ensured that personal bias was not introduced as the study progressed. **Epistemology.** This refers to the awareness of how knowledge claims are justified by staying as close to the participants

as possible during the study to obtain firsthand information. Guba and Lincoln, as cited by Creswell (2019), state that on the epistemological assumption, the researcher attempted to lessen the distance between themselves and the participants. He suggests that being a researcher he or she collaborates, spends time in the field with participants, and becomes an ‘insider’. The intention of this study was to gather information from the realities of perspective of teachers on the influence of internet slang on the writing and speaking skills of the students. The researcher followed the guidelines set by DepEd and the Inter Agency Task Force (IATF). It was assured that there is an establishment of close interaction with the participants to gain direct information that would shed light on the knowledge behind the inquiry. Axiology. It refers to the role of values in research. Creswell (2019) avers that the role of values in a study was significant. Axiology suggests that the researcher openly discusses values that shape the narrative and includes their interpretation in conjunction with the interpretation of participants. Upholding the dignity and value of every detail of information obtained from the participants was ensured by the researcher. The researcher understood the personal and value-laden nature of the information gathered from the study. Therefore, the researcher preserved the merit of the participants’ answers and carefully interpreted them in light of the participants’ own interpretations. Rhetoric. This philosophical assumption stressed that the researcher may write in a literary, informal style using the personal voice and use qualitative terms and limited definition. In the context of the study, the researcher used the first person in the elucidation of the perspective of teachers on the influence of internet slang on the writing and speaking skills of the students.

2.2. *Qualitative Assumptions*—Methodology is different from method. Methodology is a creative and responsive approach to understanding questions and subject matter, while

method refers to the exact knowledge and procedure (Gerodias, cited in Ferolino, 2021). In this study, the lived experiences and perspectives of teachers on the influence of internet slang on the writing and speaking skills of the students were investigated, particularly those participants from Sta Ana National High School, Division of Davao City. The researcher’s drive to know the deeper meaning of their experiences became the basis for doing qualitative research, a means of which is considered helpful in looking for meanings and motivations that underlie cultural symbols, personal experiences, and phenomena. By using phenomenology, it was hoped that this need would be addressed by bringing the stories of the floating teachers in a manner that, as David (2005) wrote, the themes, symbols, and meaning of the experiences were presented. Phenomenological research is based on two premises. The first is that experience is a valid, rich, and rewarding source of knowledge; this experience is a source of knowledge and shapes one’s behavior. From the definition, human experience is viewed as a cornerstone of knowledge about human phenomena and not as an unreliable source. The second premise of phenomenological research lies in the view that the everyday world is a valuable and productive source of knowledge, and that we can learn much about ourselves and reap key insights into the nature of an event by analyzing how it occurs in our daily lives. By doing phenomenology which concerns with that “what” and the “how” (Moustakas, 1995), the researcher projected that the subjective experiences, challenges and coping mechanisms of the physical education teachers were explored, and insights were drawn as basis for the possible future researches and policy analysis in relation to this research.

2.3. *Design and Procedure*—This study employed a qualitative approach to research, specifically a phenomenological research design, since it focused on the lived experiences

and perspective of teachers on the influence of internet slang on the writing and speaking skills of the students. According to Creswell (2019), phenomenology is an approach to qualitative research that focuses on the commonality of lived experiences within a particular group. The fundamental goal of the approach is to arrive at a description of the nature of the particular phenomenon. Typically, interviews were conducted with a group of individuals who have first-hand knowledge of an event, situation or experience. Other forms of data, such as documents, observations, and art, were also used. The data were read and reread, and then culled for phrases and themes, which were grouped into clusters of meanings. Through this process, the researcher was able to construct the universal meaning of the event, situation, or experience and arrived at a more profound understanding of the phenomenon. This research employed a qualitative phenomenological approach, which aims to explore how participants interpret their personal experiences. Data collection involved participants responding to questions via Google Forms, with some also participating in in-depth, face-to-face interviews when appropriate. The responses were analyzed to identify recurring themes and patterns, providing insight into their shared experiences (Jamon Cabanes, 2019). The choice of a phenomenological design was suitable because it allowed an in-depth exploration of teachers' individual experiences during the new normal in Philippine public education. A total of ten school administrators took part, offering direct insights into their experiences with this educational shift. The collected data were recorded, transcribed, and validated to capture authentic accounts of the strengths, challenges, opportunities, and threats faced in the new normal from the perspective of secondary teachers. The data analysis followed the Colaizzi method, consistent with phenomenological research standards. Participation was voluntary, with informed consent obtained, and all ethical guidelines and health protocols were strictly observed to ensure participant safety. Phenomenology is a qualitative methodology that emphasizes understanding the shared essence of lived experiences within a specific group. It seeks to describe the fundamental nature of a phenomenon by examining individuals' everyday experiences while setting aside preconceived notions. Essentially, phenomenological studies aim to gain a deeper insight into how people perceive and interpret their experiences, which aligns with the objectives of this study. As explained by Creswell and Creswell (2018), the qualitative aspect involved conducting interviews and focus groups to gather educators' perspectives on collaborative teaching practices and professional collaboration within learning communities. These methods provided a comprehensive view of participants' perceptions and experiences. Researchers adopting a phenomenological approach assume that individuals interpret their experiences through a universal underlying structure. They analyze participants' feelings, perceptions, and beliefs to uncover the core essence of the phenomenon. It is essential for researchers to bracket their own assumptions, ensuring that their biases do not influence the findings. In essence, phenomenological research aims to understand the commonality of experiences by exploring the perspectives of those who have lived through them. This approach is frequently used to study personal experiences, deepen understanding of human thought processes, and expand knowledge about specific phenomena. For instance, it can be applied to explore issues like workplace antisocial behavior, women's experiences with particular health conditions, among others. In this study, the focus was on teachers' feelings and perceptions regarding current challenges in school management. Regardless of the specific qualitative method employed, researchers must remain focused on the research questions and avoid influencing participants' responses. Es-

establishing rapport and demonstrating empathy are vital to gaining genuine insights into their experiences. Withal, based on the statements of Quad (2016), the researcher transcribed and typed the data into a computer file, in order to analyze it after interviewing. Interviews were beneficial for uncovering the story behind a participant's experiences and pursuing in-depth information around a topic. The researcher collected data, typically via extended interviews, from individuals who have experienced the phenomenon under investigation. Next, the data analysis involved triangulation, which extracted significant statements from the transcribed interviews. The significant statements were transformed into clusters of meanings according to how each statement fell under specific psychological and phenomenological concepts. Moreover, these transformations were tied together to form a general description of the experience, encompassing both the textural description of what was experienced and the structural description of how it was experienced. The researcher incorporated his or her meaning of the experiences here. Finally, the report was written such that readers understand better the essential, invariant structure of the essence of the experience. Conversely, several challenges have been pointed out. The researcher required a solid grounding in the philosophical guidelines of phenomenology. The subjects that were selected into the study were individuals who have actually experienced the phenomenon. The researcher needed to bracket his or her own experiences and observations, which was difficult to do. The researcher needed to decide as to how and when his or her personal observations were to be incorporated into the study. Epistemologically, phenomenological approaches were as based on the paradigm of personal knowledge and subjectivity, and emphasized the importance of personal perspective and interpretation. As such they were a powerful tool for understanding subjective experience, gaining

insights into people's motivations and actions, and cutting through the cluster of taken-for-granted assumptions and conventional wisdom. Since the focus of this study was to explore and assess the teacher experience and feelings towards the school environment and on the perspectives of English teachers, the researcher intended to employ the phenomenology type of qualitative method research.

2.4. Ethical Considerations—The ethical considerations are significant in the design of this research study. The researcher needed to consider several ethical issues about the research participants in this fieldwork. Ethical considerations can be specified as one of the most important parts of the research. The researcher needs to adhere to promote the aims of the research, imparting authentic knowledge, truth, and prevention of error. Social Value. Research is essential to society. In this study, the social value was focused on the experiences of teachers. This study was conducted explicitly among the elementary teachers. This study also served as a basis for the higher authorities to create more programs and resolutions where classroom teachers could benefit. Thus, the social problem that interests the researcher is the challenges faced by teachers in using interactive media instruction in the classroom to enhance teaching competence. Informed Consent. In the conduct and practice of this study, the book *Ethical Issues in Social Work Practice*, coordinated by Antonio Sandu and Ana Frunză (2018), presents the ethical framework of social work, as well as the ethical approach to the various issues raised by this field, which was considered in this section. The invitation to the participants ensured that their participation in the research is entirely voluntary, and is based on the understanding of adequate information. The participant recruitment and selection are outlined in the appendices of this study. Gaining the trust and support of research participants is critical to the informed and ethical academic inquiry and

phenomenological research. All participants were given an informed consent form before scheduling the interviews and participating in the phenomenological research process. Each participant was required to provide a signed personal acknowledgement, consent, and an indication of a willingness to participate in the study release. The purpose of the informed consent letter was to introduce the research effort, provide contact information, articulate the intent of the study, request voluntary participation by the recipients, and anticipate the information that the informants were expected to provide. All participants were required to sign and return the letter of consent to the researcher before participating in the research. Vulnerability of Research Participants. The participants in this study were capable of answering the research instrument, as they are all professional teachers in public elementary schools. Thus, the researcher assured them that they could easily reach him or her through the contact number and address in case they had any clarifications or questions regarding the study. Risks, Benefits and Safety. The recruitment of the respondents was free of coercion, undue influence or inducement. Moreover, respondents were provided with the contact numbers of the chair of the panel or panel members in case they have queries related to the study. Furthermore, in the event that respondents would experience potential discomfort and inconvenience while answering the questions, they were not compelled to participate in any manner. Further, the researcher has ensured that the respondents were safe during the conduct of the survey and interview. Thus, the distribution of the questionnaire was conducted in a safe venue and administered at their convenience. Dominant concern of this study is the Treaty Principle of Protection, as reflected in the respect for the rights of privacy and confidentiality, and minimization of risk. This was done by assigning pseudonyms for each informant so as not to disclose their identity. The possi-

bility of a degree of risk inherent to this was minimized through taking all reasonable steps to guarantee participant confidentiality. Privacy and Confidentiality of Information. This study observed the Data Privacy Act of 2002 to ensure that the data cannot be traced back to their real sources to protect participants' identities. Thus, utmost care was taken to ensure the anonymity of the data sources. Hence, any printed output that was carried out from this study was kept anonymous. Furthermore, all the issues were considered so that there was no conflict of interest between the researcher and the respondents. Any type of misleading information, as well as the representation of primary data findings in a biased way, must be avoided. Justice. The respondents were informed of the researcher's role and their corresponding role during data gathering. They were briefed that they have to give their full honesty in answering the survey questions and additionally, any communication in relation to the research should be done with honesty. Similarly, they were informed that they were the ones to benefit first from the results of the study. Transparency. The study's results were accessed by the respondents and heads of participating schools, as the information was available and could be placed on CD or other storage devices, which the researcher could provide upon request. In addition, by learning from the results of the study, classroom teachers were aware of the significance of the study and its contribution to their well-being. Further, each participant will be advised that they have the right to withdraw their information at any time up to the completion of the data collection process, and that they can be requested and allowed to verify their transcript after the interview is carried out. This provided the participants with the opportunity to amend or remove any information that they feel might identify them. The researcher reserved the right to employ the use of pseudonyms, and changing names and or non-significant dates in the interest of the protection

of the identity of the participant in all subsequent data analysis and reporting. Qualification of the Researcher. The researcher ensured that he or she possessed the needed qualifications to conduct the study. The researcher must complete the academic requirements, pass the comprehensive examination, and have passed the thesis writing stage before obtaining the master's degree. Additionally, the researcher must be qualified to conduct the study in terms of physical, mental, emotional, and financial well-being. In addition, the advisee-adviser tandem ensured that the study reached its completion. Adequacy of Facilities. The researcher aimed to complete the study successfully within the specified timeframe and to have access to the necessary resources. Likewise, the technical committee helped in the enhancement of the paper by giving the needed suggestions and recommendations for the improvement of the study. Also, the researcher ensured that he or she had enough funds to continue and finish the research. Thus, this study was hoped to be completed on time. Community Involvement. The researcher showed respect to the local tradition, culture, and views of the respondents in this study. Moreover, this study did not involve any use of deceit at any stage of its implementation, specifically in the recruitment of the participants or the methods of data collection. Furthermore, the researcher expressed great pleasure at the wholehearted participation of the interviewees in the conduct of the study. Plagiarism and Fabrication as the researcher. The researcher respected other works by properly citing the author and rewriting what someone else has said in their own words. The researcher also used quotes to indicate that the text has been taken from another paper. Similarly, the researcher assured that honesty was present in working on the manuscript and no intentional misrepresentation or making up of data or results was included, or purposefully put forward conclusions that were not accurate.

2.5. *Research Participants*—The participants of this study will be the seven teachers of Sta Ana National High School, Division of Davao City. The participants were chosen based on the following criteria: (1) must have been in the service for at least 5 years; (2) must have a very satisfactory rating in the new normal IPCRF; and (3) must be teaching an English class. This research employed a purposive sampling method, selecting participants based on specific criteria relevant to the study's objectives. In qualitative research, purposive sampling—also known as judgmental, selective, or subjective sampling—is a common non-probability sampling approach. It involves choosing participants who meet predefined criteria aligned with the research goals (Etikan et al., 2022). Campbell et al. (2020) support this, noting that purposive sampling is advantageous when the aim is to gain an in-depth understanding of a particular experience, event, or environment. This method ensures that resources are directed toward cases most likely to provide valuable and relevant information. Additionally, Tracy (2020) highlights the significance of purposive sampling, stating that proficient qualitative researchers intentionally select data that directly relates to their research questions and objectives.

2.6. *Role of the Researcher*—The researcher has a responsibility to uncover, transfer, and exploit knowledge for the benefit of educational institutions. To do so, the researcher takes up the following roles in the course of the study: Facilitator and Promoter of Unbiased Research. The researcher conducts interviews with the participants and guides them in the process. The researcher interprets ideas and responses based on existing literature and related studies, and not on the researcher's knowledge, thoughts, and feelings, to avoid the intrusion of bias. Expert in qualitative methods. The researcher implements the qualitative method correctly. To do so, the researcher assesses

himself and seeks help from the research adviser and other research professionals. These help him exhibit competence in explaining the study without biasing the participants, conducting interviews properly according to the design, making appropriate field observations, selecting appropriate artifacts, images, and journal portions, and employing Environmental Triangulation and Thematic Content Analysis precisely. Collector and Keeper of data. The researcher ensured different ways of making a record of what is said and done during the interview and Focus Group Discussion, such as taking handwritten notes or audio and/or video recording. The recordings were transcribed verbatim before data analysis could begin. Records done by the researcher were secured correctly, as they contain sensitive information and were relevant to the research. However, the data were being collected, a primary responsibility of the researcher was to safeguard participants and their data. Mechanisms for such safeguarding must be clearly articulated to participants and must be approved by a relevant research ethics review board before the research begins. Analyst of data. The researcher saw the phenomenon or problem from the participants' perspective by interpreting data, transcribing and checking, reading between the lines, coding, and theming. The researcher made sure that the findings were accurate to the participants and that their voices were heard. Organizer and presenter of data. The researcher presented the problem and the related literature and studies that support it. Findings of the study were presented too, by research question, stating the results for each one by using themes to show how the research questions were answered in the study. Moreover, the researcher provided future directions and implications of the study to inform the improvement of educational policy and practices.

2.7. Data Collection—The following was the step-by-step process of gathering the data needed. Asking permission from the Schools

Division Superintendent. The researcher asked permission from the Schools Division Superintendent to conduct the study in the identified school. The researcher sent a letter addressed to the Schools Division Superintendent, accompanied by Chapters 1 and 2 and the research instrument. These documents explain the study's objectives and participant identification. The researcher waited for the response of the SDS before conducting it. After securing the approval of the SDS, the researcher sent letters to the principals of the schools, explaining the study to be conducted in their schools. Obtaining consent from the participants. The researcher asked permission from the participants and their parents/guardians. They were formally oriented about the study and the process they would go through as participants. Conducting the interview. The researcher conducted the in-depth interview using the interview questionnaire. The profile of the participants was taken, notes were jotted down, and conversations were recorded using a sound recorder for ease of transcription. The researcher carefully listened and responded actively during the interviews. Transcribing the responses of the interviewees. The researcher transcribed the responses of the interviewees precisely by recalling their answers from the sound recorder. Since the participants used their vernacular language, the researcher translated it into English. Data Coding and thematizing. After the transcription, the data were then categorized and coded. Then, themes were extracted, and individual data from the participants were compared and contrasted. The researcher then conducted a second round of interviews (FGD) to corroborate any data that needed further explanation and input from the participants. Additional information gathered was examined thoroughly and integrated into the existing body of data. After which, the data were compared and contrasted between the participants in order to come up with patterns and trends.

2.8. *Data Analysis*—In this study, thematic analysis was employed to analyze the gathered data. The researcher analyzed the participants' answers from the conducted interviews using Creswell's Model, specifically the identifying of themes approach. According to Creswell (2012), themes in qualitative research are similar codes aggregated together to form a major idea in the database. Familiarization with the data was common to all forms of qualitative analysis; the researcher immersed herself in and became intimately familiar with the data, reading and re-reading the data and noting any initial analytic observations. Coding is also a common element of many approaches to qualitative analysis, involving generating pithy labels for important features of the data of relevance to the (broad) research question guiding the analysis. Coding is not simply a method of data reduction; it is also an analytic process, so codes capture both a semantic and conceptual reading of the data. The researcher coded every data item and ended this phase by collating all their codes and relevant data extracts. Searching for themes was a coherent and meaningful pattern in the data relevant to the research question. The researcher ended this phase by collating all the coded data relevant to each theme. Reviewing themes. The researcher reflected on whether the themes tell a convincing and compelling story about the data, and began to define the nature of each theme and the relationship between the themes. Defining and naming themes: The researcher prepared a detailed analysis of each theme, identifying the 'essence' of each theme and constructing a concise, punchy, and informative name for each theme. Writing up involves weaving together the analytic narrative and data extracts to tell the reader a coherent and persuasive story about the data, and contextualizing it in relation to existing literature. The researcher ensured that the experiences and perspectives of teachers on the influence of internet slang on the writing and speaking skills

of students were presented comprehensively.

2.9. *Analytical Framework*—The framework coding and categorization system systematically organizes data to facilitate the answering of research questions. This structured method of data analysis helps researchers summarize and condense extensive datasets. Braun Clarke (2022) emphasize that reflexive thematic analysis involves the researcher actively engaging in the processes of coding and developing themes. This approach requires the researcher to continually reflect on their assumptions and practices, recognizing how these influence the interpretation of the data. The core principles of thematic analysis—such as coding data, pinpointing themes, refining these themes, and presenting the results—are also relevant to other qualitative approaches like discourse analysis (Flick, 2022). Essentially, thematic analysis is a qualitative technique used to examine data by uncovering and interpreting recurring patterns within it (Liebenberg et al., 2020). Braun and Clarke (2022) outlined the specific steps involved in conducting thematic analysis within their broader analytical framework. The process is enumerated:

Familiarization with Data – The researcher examined and reviewed the dataset multiple times to ensure a thorough understanding of its contents. During this process, the researcher aimed to document my initial thoughts and insights based on my observations of the data.

Generation of Codes – Begin by thoroughly and methodically examining the data supplied by the researcher. During this process, identify segments that are significant, engaging, or relevant to the research question. Develop statements that describe these segments, which are essentially the codes. This step involves close reading and interpretation of the data, but it remains grounded in the content. Remember, each code should represent a single meaningful unit.

Forming Initial Themes – Next, look for common patterns of meaning across the entire

Fig. 2. Analytical Framework of the Study

dataset. Group related codes together to form preliminary themes that help address your research questions. This phase requires a more abstract level of thinking, where you move beyond individual codes to recognize broader concepts that connect multiple codes. Each theme should encompass at least two related codes, providing a cohesive understanding.

Reviewing Themes – Once initial themes are established, verify their relevance and coherence with the data. Check whether the themes accurately reflect the codes and whether they effectively respond to the research questions. This stage involves critical thinking, where you challenge and refine your themes to ensure they are well-founded and meaningful.

Refining, Defining, and Naming Themes – Further develop each theme by ensuring it is centered around a clear, core idea. Ask yourself: What does this theme reveal? How does it contribute to answering the research question? This step entails crafting the narrative that explains your findings. Define each theme precisely, articulating what it signifies and how it enhances understanding. Additionally, assign a concise and descriptive name to each theme to facilitate clarity and communication.

Reporting Findings – Finally, synthesize the analytical insights into a comprehensive narrative. Incorporate illustrative data excerpts that support each theme and directly address the research questions. This stage involves writing the manuscript, where you present your findings, connecting the analysis to the broader research context.

2.10. Trustworthiness of the Study—The concepts of validity and reliability were relatively foreign to the field of qualitative research. Qualitative researchers substitute data trustworthiness instead of focusing on reliability and validity. Trustworthiness consists of the components such as credibility, transferability, dependability, and conformability (Harts, 2016). Credibility involves establishing that the findings of the research are credible or believable from the perspective of the participant. Through

observing the attributes of prolonged engagement, credibility contributes to a belief in the trustworthiness of data. To address the issue of credibility, the researcher interviewed as many research participants as possible, or up to the point of saturation. Meanwhile, transferability is the degree to which the findings can be generalized or transferred to other contexts. In this, the researcher did a thorough job of describing the research context and assumptions that are relevant. On the other hand, depend-

ability was the consistency and repeatability of the research. The researcher made sure that the findings of the study were evaluated by the participants and scrutinized by an external reviewer. Lastly, conformability is the degree to which findings can be confirmed or corroborated by other researchers. The researcher documented the procedures and rechecked the data during the entire research process. The researcher also made sure that the findings were free from bias.

3. Results and Discussion

In this chapter, the study's results are presented and discussed about its aim. Moreover, the themes that emerged from the gathered data are discussed in this chapter. The results present the description and background of the participants, who are assigned pseudonyms to conceal their identities

3.1. The Perspectives of Teachers on the Students' Use Of Internet "Lingo" In English Class—New communication technologies and emerging media cultures have profoundly affected the world; technological advances have demonstrated a dramatic shift in how individuals communicate. Kern (2024) notes that the rapid evolution of communication technologies has transformed language pedagogy and language use, enabling new forms of discourse, new types of authorship, and new ways to create and participate in communities. Nowadays, internet communication is an essential and valuable part of life, whether the user is nineteen or ninety, a teacher or an engineer; the internet is ubiquitous in society. It has dramatically changed how people communicate and use English, both in writing and speech. While this new form of language has benefits, it also presents some challenges that English teachers have observed in their students' written and oral language. The participants' responses were narrowed down to generate themes and subthemes. These were carefully analyzed and formulated based on the informants' accounts and reflec-

tions.

Benefits of Internet Language – Evokes Emotions. For the participants, the environment has become increasingly interconnected through various messaging platforms, including text messages, online chat, messengers, and emails. Applications like Facebook, Instagram, Twitter, and WhatsApp may also reveal changes that have recently occurred in English. The internet has given rise to what is essentially a new English variety, which is distinct from traditional types. The spread of Internet communication has reached every level of society, every profession, age, and gender. The participants believe that there is an advantage to using internet slang. It can help students evoke emotions in conversations or written discourse. They shared:

Internet language also provides endless opportunities for fun because of its limitless, sometimes nonsensical, and constantly changing nature. The participants observed that the students can easily describe things, people, and ideas using internet language. They can freely express themselves without the restrictions of limited

English vocabulary acquisition.

It has been claimed that slang is created to freshen the language, to vitalize it, to make the language more pungent and picturesque, to increase the store of terse and striking words, or to provide a vocabulary for new shades of meaning. Most of the originators and purveyors of slang, however, are probably not conscious of these noble purposes and do not seem overly concerned about what happens to their language (Saliloko, S.M.; 2020).

Learning a language needs to be about more than just reading textbooks and learning how to reproduce what you learn. Textbooks will provide language learners with the basics, including the rules of the language and primary adjectives and nouns. In order to become truly fluent, however, a language learner must understand how to be current. It also helps you communicate with people throughout different regions within a country. Understanding internet language means a person will understand the variations within language and different dialects across a nation (Walton, 2019). Improves students' creativity. Creativity is the skill of bringing about something new and valuable into existence. Creative people innovate toward newness; they often find a series of alternative solutions and can make sound decisions quickly. In learning a language, creativity is the ability to create, and creating means producing original and valuable ideas by combining elements and forms that already exist. Nowadays, students combine different forms of language to express themselves more effectively. Combinations are usually the use of standard and internet language. The study participants gained valuable insights related to this topic. They noted:

The responses of the participants imply that the internet is a learning tool. It plays an important role in helping students creatively express themselves. Social media platforms and instant messaging apps have reached a significant dominance in our society. Students nowadays are

very active and engaged on these kinds of platforms and apps. Most of them have experience sharing their thoughts and ideas, and they express them in creative ways. Teachers are taking advantage of this to bring such creativity to English class. However, designing a lesson that fosters the creativity of students requires important skills. The participants of the study provided strategic recommendations for teachers to utilize the internet in class effectively. They noted:

The participants suggest that a rigid language class kills creativity. Tight and heavy standards offer fewer opportunities for students to exercise the extent of their creative ability. Teachers need to be more flexible and allow students to learn and study in their most comfortable and confident way. They also emphasized that by doing so, teachers should not ignore the importance of teaching students the proper and formal way of a language. Correct grammar, spelling, and punctuation should be taught and reinforced to students, enabling them to maintain a professional tone in their work, which is essential for future employment. In general, the responses of the participants relate to the findings of McCabe (2014), which suggest that creativity is a skill of utmost importance in all areas of life. It is not only a tool to help students become more comfortable, but it has also been shown to improve language learning. It is internet language that enriches and makes the standard English language more creative than before. Therefore, it could be used to foster or unleash the creativity of students needed for English language development. Furthermore, the statement by Al-Salman Saeed (2017) verifies the participants' responses. Teachers indeed need to be conscious and aware that, as times have changed, the exposure to internet language manifests also in the writing and speaking of students. Without being too rigid and strict, which can kill creativity, teachers should impose proper regulations on internet use. While using

internet language for creative self-expression, teachers should not overlook the importance of teaching students the appropriate way and setting in which formal writing and speaking should be used.

3.2. *Challenges of Internet Language* — Multiple and conflicting meanings. Slang is the use of terms and phrases of high informality that are not considered standard in the dialect or language of the speaker. Slangs are unique to literature and culture, but are also transferred from one culture and language to another. Recent electronic communications make a significant contribution to this process. Abbreviations and acronyms are parts of the Internet slang or language. The participants noticed that students in this generation like to use different abbreviations in their sentences.

The participants expressed that they had difficulty in grasping the meaning of the abbreviations that the students used. There are some that they can adequately understand, but mostly they fail to recognize the meaning. They shared:

Furthermore, the participants observed that while some students do not get confused with the abbreviations they use, others misinterpret them because abbreviations can have multiple meanings. They conveyed:

While Internet slang shortcuts save time for the writer, they take twice as long for the reader to understand. According to the participants, since Internet language is constantly changing, it is difficult to provide a standardized definition, thereby taking time for the receiver to process the intended message

Prescriptivists tend to have the widespread belief that the Internet has a negative influence on the future of language, and that it would lead to a degradation of the standard. Some would even attribute any decline in standard formal English to the increase in usage of electronic communication. It has also been suggested that the linguistic differences between Standard English and CMC can have implications for literacy edu-

cation. This is illustrated by the widely reported example of a school essay submitted by a Scottish teenager, which contained many abbreviations and acronyms likened to SMS language. There was great condemnation of this style by the mass media as well as educationists, who expressed that this showed diminishing literacy or linguistic abilities (Zappavigna, 2012). On the other hand, descriptivists have counter-argued that the Internet allows better expressions of a language. Rather than established linguistic conventions, linguistic choices sometimes reflect personal taste. It has also been suggested that, as opposed to intentionally flouting language conventions, Internet slang is a result of a lack of motivation to monitor speech online. Hale and Scanlon describe language in emails as being derived from "writing the way people talk", and that there is no need to insist on 'Standard' English. English users have an extensive tradition of etiquette guides, instead of traditional prescriptive treatises, that offer pointers on linguistic appropriateness. Using and spreading Internet slang also adds to the cultural currency of a language. It is important to the speakers of the language due to the foundation it provides for identifying within a group, and for defining a person's individual linguistic and communicative competence. The result is a specialized subculture based on its use of slang (Morgan, 2020). Excessive use of internet language. Social media slang has adversely affected the verbal and written skills of students. Students show poor performance in reading and writing. According to the participants, students frequently use excessive slang in their written assignments and papers, and they also exhibit poor reading performance. The reasons are quite apparent; students spend prolonged hours on social media communicating with their friends in slang, which has badly affected their written and verbal skills. High school teachers report that they get English essays they have never seen before in their teaching career.

For participants growing up in a technological era, high school students may be unaware that they are using excessive internet language in the classroom. The increased use of social media slang has also enhanced its presence in the classroom, and spelling grammar mistakes are quite commonly found.

The participants believed that using incomplete words and phrases is acceptable in informal settings. However, they noted that if students consistently use this practice in exams and assignments, it can negatively impact their grades and academic performance. They further observed that the writing composition of the students is far from the academic writing standards. They conveyed:

There is a measure of uncertainty as to whether college admissions officials will adapt to this social change in language, or if future prospective college students will need to be mindful and observant of the words they use. The participants believed that an educated student coming out of high school should be adaptive. Those who do not adapt will have difficulty securing slots in college.

According to Gilmore (2021), students who spend all day online may struggle to commu-

These themes imply that the future remains unclear as generations of students continue to grow up with a rapid rate of technological advancement that incorporates internet language. Teachers must continue to emphasize the distinction between professional writing and slang to students, as it is essential for them to understand this difference. As social media continues to grow, students must decide whether to use internet slang to sound cool or to limit its use and succeed in reading, writing, and other skills.

Teachers Dealing with the Challenges Of the Internet “Lingo” In the Students’ Learning Of the English Language – Introducing Slang to English Language Learners Introducing Slang to

nicate in class when they rely heavily on slang terms. When students are sending an email or communicating with a teacher in class, they may use improper language in their communication. According to a survey of 700 students ages 12 to 17 by the Pew Internet American Life Project, 85 % of the respondents reported using a form of electronic communication, whether it be social media, text messaging, or instant messaging. This survey suggests that some may argue that students should not have to change their slang terms; instead, adults should learn these terms to understand what students are reading and writing. This is misguided as students should know not to use these terms in the classroom as it is not used in the workforce today (Gilmore, 2021). The framework below summarizes the perspectives of teachers on the students’ use of internet “lingo” in English class. Based on the figure 3, the themes that emerged from the participants’ responses regarding the benefits of internet language evoke emotions and enhance students’ creativity. In contrast, the themes that emerged from the challenges of internet language were multiple and conflicting, including the excessive use of internet language.

English Language Learners In a context where English is taught as a foreign language, It is typically taught and used exclusively in class, often in the formal, standard use of the language, i.e., Standard English. For instance, English learners are introduced to the ready-made textbooks and audios for speaking classes, which are supposed to provide them with great opportunities to learn how to use the language in their “real world” interactions for communication. However, English language learners usually go through experiences where they find that the language they have learned in class is different from what they hear or use as they interact with native users of the language. Accord-

Fig. 3. Emerging Themes on the Perspectives of Teachers on the Students' Use of Internet "Lingo" in English Class

ingly, they learn to “modify the way they speak” through the experiences they come across while interacting with people and online. This helps them gain social acceptance and construct their identity. By using slang, students learn to modify their speech by using certain expressions and making changes in pronunciation and grammar (Meyerhoff, 2011). English language teachers’ aim should not be to help ELLs learn the academic language, but also to help them master the social language. It is essential to help them understand and master the social and academic language. The participants’ responses were condensed to identify the themes and subthemes. These were carefully analyzed and formulated based on the information provided by the informants’ accounts and reflections. Engaging students in both digital social communications and formal academic discourse. Since technology has become an integral part of everyday life, participants believe that internet language will continue to exist and influence the young generation of learners. Instead of prohibiting its use, they prefer to expose students to various contexts that require both academic and social (internet) language. The participants shared:

The participants asserted that the main point of showing students how to use other varieties of language (both formal and informal) is to present to them examples of its appropriate use it. Learning to use the informal language will prevent them from misusing or overusing internet slang or informal varieties. They shared:

Drouin (2011) argued that technology is here to stay, and internet language is the primary mode of communication used by the net generation. Parents and teachers must make a difficult choice: either accept and recognize it as a skillful dialect or reject it as an unorthodox alien language. It is essential to recognize that humans are naturally inclined to acquire the language and dialects around them. Therefore, the next generation cannot be blamed for developing the capacity to process, analyze, and evalu-

ate these messages and adeptly produce a reply to share opinions, ideas, personal experiences, and narratives. If Standard English is considered a dialect of English, then the new language promoted by the techno-savvy generation could be seen as a newer dialect of the English language. Schools should not limit English learning based on standards, but also venture into emerging languages. Interestingly, researchers found that there is a positive relationship between frequent text messaging, reading fluency, and spelling accuracy. Widening vocabulary and sentence mastery. The expansion of a student’s vocabulary is a key factor for helping the learners develop an understanding of both social (internet ‘lingo’) and academic language. The participants voiced that it is important to develop students’ word acquisition in order for them to successfully put in print the thoughts and ideas they want to share. They stated that they have vocabulary drills, reading comprehension activities, spelling drills, and many more activities in every class session since they believe that these activities can broaden the students’ world of words, thereby improving their language skills. The participants expressed:

The participants also believe that students should repetitively use the words they learned in order for them to store them in their long-term memory. One way to use it is they associate words with their experiences or memories so that they have the ability to recall them as it has influenced their life. This aims to enhance students’ associative memory by allowing them to practice retrieving associations, thereby strengthening synaptic connections in the brain and improving their ability to recall information more quickly. They shared:

This corroborates the idea of Cuncic (2021), who asserted that the value in developing associative memory capabilities has far-reaching implications for daily life. Establishing associations helps people to remember information more easily, such as names of people and places,

phone numbers, birthdays and anniversaries. This may help them to recall other related information about them. It also helps people to remember things in an efficient manner by recalling information that is useful for specific tasks. In general, if students can spell, recognize, and use a word in the proper format, both written and verbally, then they have mastered that word. According to Joshi Roth (2009), the true goal of the English system extends beyond spelling and pronunciation in communication, and the final test is whether or not meaning can be conveyed and understood in both written and oral forms. English can be tricky because many words sound the same when pronounced but are spelled differently and, therefore, have a completely different meaning. For example, the words rain, rein, and reign all have very different meanings, but all sound the same and may be a point of confusion for a user of English vocabulary. Because the English language is complex to master, the best way for a person to achieve proper understanding, according to experts, is to establish a connection between reading comprehension, vocabulary, and spelling. The path to reading and writing fluently in English is through mastering the connections between letter combinations and the sounds they represent. Giving feedback. Frequent and effective feedback increases students' productivity and creativity. Many teachers feel uncertain about themselves when providing feedback on students' language performance. They do not wish to stifle students' creativity or expression of themselves. They may even feel that appreciation of their skill is so subjective that comments that are at all critical may be unfair. The participants stressed that feedback is a key element of the incremental process of students' language performance. Teachers should know how to deliver feedback to students appropriately. Providing frequent and ongoing feedback is a significant means of improving students' achievement. They believe that effective feed-

back helps students reflect on their learning and learning strategies, enabling them to make adjustments for better progress. The participants shared:

Furthermore, they noted that when students are trying to learn new skills, they need to receive feedback indicating whether they are on the right track. Both the mastery of content and, more importantly, the mastery of how to think require trial-and-error learning. However, for them, there is also a downside to feedback, as not all can be effective, especially if it is presented in a solely negative or correct way. They shared:

Moreover, timely feedback is necessary for the participant so that students would still have a fresh association and reflection on the feedback given. One of them voiced:

This finding is congruent with the notion of Brown (2001), who asserted that giving feedback in the learning process is important to improve students' performance. It is provided as a source of information about the students' strengths and weaknesses in their performance, enabling them to make improvements. Feedback is information that is given to the learner to improve their performance. Giving feedback means telling learners about the progress they are making as well as guiding them to areas for improvement. Through feedback given, learners are expected to be able to focus and concentrate more on what is being learned. Furthermore, feedback from a teacher helps learners become more aware of their strengths and weaknesses in a learning course, enabling them to use their strengths to overcome their weaknesses by understanding the feedback provided. Based on Figure 4, three themes emerged from the participants' responses: engaging students in both digital social communications and formal academic discourse, expanding vocabulary and sentence mastery, and providing feedback. These themes suggest that real-life conversations do not always involve formal spoken interactions;

Fig. 4. Emerging themes on the Teachers dealing with the challenges of Internet “lingo” in the students’ learning of the English language

learning to use internet slang can facilitate convergence, divergence, and maintenance, which are key components of speech accommodation theory. In other words, how individuals become familiar with each other’s linguistic features during speech. In the case of students, they needed to gain social approval in their new community, which made convergence occur. They use inter-

net language to maintain their social approval and construct their identity. Teachers must be open to imparting both formal and informal English in order to ease students’ adaptation to the community. Teachers may also use the different languages’ benefits to make the classroom more meaningful and dynamic.

3.3. Educational Management Insights Drawn From the Experience of the Teachers— The participants shared their educational management insights, which were then narrowed down to generate the themes. These themes were carefully analyzed and formulated based on the information provided by participants’ accounts and reflections. The subthemes are shown below: Internet language improves student motivation. Today’s young generation of students comes from the era of vast and new communication technologies and emerging media cultures. They are labelled as the Net Generation. Since students are familiar with communication technologies and media cultures, they

can relate to the situation and have the motivation to learn through them. The participants of the study share their insights that:

The responses of the participants imply that internet language enables students to be immersed in an English class. English teachers are embracing internet language. They accept the idea that students nowadays are into communication technologies and media culture. Teachers utilize this interest of the students to catch their attention and make them participate in class. This sounds easy, but designing lessons that incorporate internet language is a significant task for teachers. They shared strategic recommendations for teachers. These are:

According to the participants' responses, teachers treat internet language the same as standard English language when designing lessons. They emphasized that the language used on the internet should be suitable for the reading and comprehension skills of the students. Moreover, like standard English language, internet language should be introduced appropriately and unlocked to ensure that students understand it. The researcher agrees with the responses of the participants. The digital divide still exists. Not all students have computers and an internet connection at home, which is why there is still a possibility that not all students are familiar with the internet language. Hence, teachers need to treat internet language, just like the standard English language, when designing a lesson. In general, the responses of the participants coincide with the statement of Novak Anderson (2020) that framing lessons in student-centric rather than teacher-centric ways can encourage engagement and persistence in learning. An example of this is using or introducing internet language in class, in which students are highly interested and familiar. Novak Anderson (2020) have shown that students who learn in student-centric ways are more confident and are better able to articulate their thoughts and opinions. These qualities are essential in learning and mastering a language. Moreover, the responses align with McCarthy's (2014) statement that student interest holds significant power. When a topic connects to what students like, engagement deepens as they willingly spend time thinking, dialoging, and creating ideas in meaningful ways. Making learning contextual to real-world experiences is a key learning technique that engages students' interests. However, Cooke, M. (2015) reminded teachers that catering to students' interests works well with instructional planning based on readiness and learning profiles. Readiness combined with interest leads to students doing work at a respectable complexity level with the familiarity of a topic that

they relate to. It also enables students to grasp concepts effectively. Internet language assists language development. Language development always occurs. Individuals always experience additional words. Especially the younger generation, they use new words among those who are not used to them. This is motivated by the current digital era, where the younger generation spends more time on social media or other online platforms compared to socializing with the surrounding community. This certainly has a significant influence on their language development, as discussed by the participants. They noted:

The participants suggest that the use of internet language is increasing because teachers find it an effective way to develop students' language skills. They imply that students found internet language easier to use and easier to understand than standard English language because they are more familiar with it and less structured. Based on the responses, teachers are taking advantage of students' familiarity and comfort with internet language to improve the language skills of the students, especially communication skills – speaking and writing. Designing a lesson incorporating the knowledge of students in internet language is a big task for a teacher. Therefore, the participants of the study gave strategic recommendations for teachers. These are:

It is clear from the responses of the participants that as teachers playfully and purposefully interact with students, they promote language development. When students have fun interactions with others, they learn several skills that help them become good communicators. Since students learn language during conversations in everyday situations and activities, it makes sense that the better the students' ability to participate in interactions with other people, the more opportunities they have to communicate and learn English. In general, the participants' responses align with Maulidiya's (2018) statement that internet language is more flexible and

simpler than standard English, which is why it is more attractive to students. They often use this language, thereby assisting in the language development of students, especially in communication. Moreover, another statement that supports the responses of the participants is the statement of Adha (2020) that with the rise of online learning platforms, the use of internet language becomes prevalent in English language classes. Students are exposed to the internet world, that is why they often use such language to express their ideas and opinions in class. Their participation enhances their communication skills and vocabulary. Internet language cannot be separated from social media, because they are one unit. The internet language also uses the English language, but its use is combined or in a playful way. Teachers need to improve their professional competence. Improving professional competence ensures that teachers acquire the knowledge and skills necessary to perform an activity efficiently in a particular work context. The participants emphasized the importance of educating teachers' minds. This helps teachers keep their professional knowledge and skills up to date. The new generation has a different approach to learning than previous generations. Professional development enables teachers to acquire new teaching techniques for students of this generation, with a focus on enhancing their language performance.

For them, trainings, seminars, and LAC sessions encourage the exchange of knowledge and best practices in teaching. The seasoned teachers can act as mentors to the new ones, and the new teachers can provide the seasoned teachers with up-to-date knowledge on the latest teaching styles and methods.

Based on the figure 5, three themes emerged from the responses of the participants in the educational management insights drawn from their experiences. These were internet language

Furthermore, through professional development teachers can acquire skills on how to effectively integrate technology to language instructions. Technology is the latest trends nowadays, the participants believe that technology interests students; hence, teachers should maximize its potential use in improving their students' language performance.

Today's teaching careers look nothing like they did 20 or even just 10 years ago. Like technology, the field of education evolves rapidly, making techniques, skills, and technologies obsolete within five to 10 years. That is why being a lifelong learner plays an important role in the educational process. It helps educators incorporate new tools and strategies into the learning process to boost their students' learning development. Lifelong learning is an essential challenge for inventing the future of societies; it is a necessity rather than a luxury to be considered. It is a mindset and a habit for people to acquire (Fischer, 2018). Educators who are lifelong learners are more successful. They can conquer challenges. People with a lifelong learning mindset treat mistakes and challenges as part of the learning process. They do not see mistakes as failures. Mistakes give them new information they can use as they continue to find ways to solve a problem or challenge. Educators never know what types of questions students will ask. Lifelong learners make learning a regular habit to adapt to changes and student actions. By embracing a student-like mindset and learning to turn self-education into a daily habit, teachers can hone their current skills and develop new ones while enriching their mind then, when the time to adapt arrives, the transitions are less bumpy (Jun, 2018).

improves student motivation, internet language assists language development, and Teacher to improve professional competence. The themes suggest that internet language gained popularity

Fig. 5. Emerging themes on the Educational Management Insights Drawn from the Experience of the Teachers

due to its widespread use among internet users. Teachers are utilizing internet language to make learning English fun and more connected to the advanced society. English teachers emphasized that the process of language learning should not revolve only around the basics of speech and written communication. Instead, it should also include the entire experience of the student, confidence, freedom, creativity, and being con-

nected with others. It was justified that there is value in learning the internet language. Internet language is the future. Teachers should embrace it, not deny it. However, they should not forget that it is important for students, too, to learn proper or formal English. They must possess the ability to convey knowledge and have a sense of occasion.

4. Implications and Future Directions

This chapter offers an overview of the research, emphasizing the main findings related to teachers' experiences and the broader implications for the education sector. It emphasizes the significance of understanding teachers' perspectives to improve teaching conditions and student outcomes. Additionally, the chapter discusses possible directions for future research, such as exploring the effects of ongoing professional development and technological integration on teachers' well-being and effectiveness, to inform strategies that support educators' growth and satisfaction.

4.1. Implications—The goal of the study was to investigate teachers' perspectives on the influence of internet slang on the writing and speaking skills of the students. The emerging themes on teachers' perspectives on students' use of internet "lingo" in English Class, under the benefits of internet language, evoke emotions and improve students' creativity. In contrast, the themes that emerged on the challenges of internet language include multiple and conflicting meanings, as well as excessive use of internet language. These themes imply that the future remains unclear as generations of students continue to grow up with a rapid rate of technology that embraces internet language. Teachers must continue to point out the difference between professional writing and slang to students, as it is crucial for them to understand this distinction. As social media continues to grow, students must decide whether to use internet slang to sound cool or to limit its use and succeed in reading, writing, and other skills. Further, the emerging themes on the teachers dealing with the challenges of internet "lingo" in the students learning of English language were engaging stu-

dents to both digital social communications and formal academic discourse, widening vocabulary and sentence mastery, and giving feedback. These themes implied that real-life conversations do not include formal spoken interactions all the time. In the case of students, they needed to gain social approval in their new community, which makes convergence occur. They use internet language to maintain their social approval and construct their identity. Teachers must be open to imparting both formal and informal English in order to ease student's adaption to the community. Teachers may also use the different language's benefits to make the classroom more meaningful and dynamic. Lastly, the emerging themes on the educational management insights drawn from the experience of the teachers were internet language improves student motivation, internet language assists language development, and Teacher to Improve professional competence. The themes imply that internet language became popular due to its heavy use by internet users. Teachers are utilizing internet language to make learning English fun and more connected to the advanced society. English teachers em-

phasized that the process of language learning should not revolve only around the basics of speech and written communication. Instead, it should also include the entire experience of the student, confidence, freedom, creativity, and being connected with others. It was justified that there is value in learning the internet language.

4.2. Future Directions —This research provides important empirical, theoretical, and practical contributions to investigate teachers' perspectives on the influence of internet slang on the writing and speaking skills of students. The data obtained had directions for various stakeholders in education, including policymakers, administrators, and teachers. The future directions of this study are as follows: Policymakers To collaborate more effectively with school leaders and teacher trainers, enabling the reform of policies related to enhancing students' language performance in a manner that is relevant and responsive, thereby providing improved support and resources for 21st-century education.

School Administrators – Aims to evaluate the application of internet "lingo" among students to improve their language skills and attitudes further. Additionally, it seeks to encourage teachers to incorporate awareness of

Internet language is the future. Teachers should embrace it, not deny it. However, they should not forget that it is important for students, too, to learn proper or formal English. It is essential that they possess the ability to convey knowledge and have a sense of occasion.

internet language into communication subjects, enabling students to utilize it effectively. The research also aims to facilitate teachers by providing necessary technical support to enhance their effectiveness in addressing students' language use in digital communication.

Teachers – To foster student engagement and encourage them to share their understanding of internet language within communication classes, it is important to recognize that students' familiarity with these linguistic styles may differ based on their level of exposure to the internet and social media platforms.

Future Researchers – Considering perspectives from educators across various subject areas, conducting further interviews with students and teachers at different grade levels will provide valuable insights. This approach will lead to more comprehensive findings and implications that are specifically aligned with the organizational structure and hierarchical context of the education sector.

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